

Composition of children pharyngeal microbiome by 16S rRNA deep sequencing

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Summary

The upper respiratory tract (URT) is colonised by a large variety of bacteria that constitute the respiratory microbiota. Most do not have a role and may even be protective. The aim of the present study was to analyse the microbiome and characterize the relative abundance of microbial communities of the pharynx by next generation sequencing of the 16S rRNA gene of bacteria in healthy children and children with a respiratory infection. Ten phyla were identified in the 8 study subjects. The most abundant phyla detected, were *Firmicutes*, *Proteobacteria* and *Bacteroidetes*, while the relative abundance of each was highly variable across the subjects. At the family, genus and species level, 24 families, 19 genera and 71 species respectively were common both in patients and healthy subjects, while some (28 families and 24 genera) were identified only in healthy subjects and few (7 families, 8 genera and 9 species) were identified only in patients. No statistically significant differences were observed in relation to the age or gender of the subjects. Interestingly, the most abundant bacteria detected in healthy children were *Strep-*

tococcus, *Prevotella*, *Moraxella*, *Veillonella* and *Leptotrichia*, while in young patients *Moraxella* was not detected among the most prevalent bacteria, supporting the notion that it may play a protective role in infection. Protective and pathogenic bacteria have been identified in healthy children and in patients. Such studies can form the basis for new approaches to fight diseases responding poorly to traditional interventions.

Key words

microbiome, 16SrRNA, respiratory, children, deep sequencing

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Introduction

The upper respiratory tract (URT) is colonised by a large variety of bacteria that constitute the respiratory microbiota. The largest fraction of microbes that colonise the URTs composed of microorganisms without any pathogenic role, generally named commensals. Potentially pathogenic bacteria are embedded in a community of commensals, forming together the nasopharyngeal microbiota. Moreover, many pathogenic species, including *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Moraxella catarrhalis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Neisseria meningitidis*, exist in the nasopharynx of apparently healthy individuals.¹

Microbial colonization succession is highly influenced by environmental factors, host factors and bacterial acquisition during the first years of life, so understanding the relationships between microbes of the URT during perturbations is anticipated to provide insights into the pathogenesis of respiratory infections.²

Advances in molecular techniques, particularly metagenomics, have allowed us to gain an insight into the symbiosis between humans and their resident microbes. Deep sequencing methods have made it possible to evaluate the whole composition of the URT microbial ecosystem, explore its diversity and relative abundance down to the species level, giving the possibility to determine its relationship to human health and disease. This complex microbial ecosystem in and on human bodies seems to play an important role in

health by stimulation of the immune system, contribution to the development of mucosal and/or epithelial barriers and containment of pathogens.^{2,3,4}

The URT microbiota varies dramatically according to the developmental stage. A one-year longitudinal study on newborn infants indicated that the nasal microbiota was primarily shaped by age, with increasing bacterial density and decreasing diversity.¹

The aim of the present study is to analyse the composition of the pharyngeal microbiome and characterize the relative abundance of microbial communities of the pharynx at the phylum, family, genus and species levels, by next generation sequencing of the 16S rRNA gene of bacteria in pharyngeal swabs samples of healthy children and children with a respiratory infection in N. Greece. This study will form the basis for further studies in our geographical area that will focus on the relationship of the URT microbiome with disease.

Materials and Methods

Eight children were eligible to the selection criteria and enrolled into the study. Their average age was 9.5 years (5-16 years of age), while half of them (50%) were male. All individuals were Greek and were residents of areas of northern Greece. None of them were vaccinated against influenza. Six of the children were healthy. The inclusion criteria requested no asthma and family hi-

story of allergy, no history of pneumonia, no cough, fever or other respiratory/allergic symptoms one month before sampling, antibiotic exposure for at least 6 months prior to the study, and no respiratory symptoms 1 week after sampling. Two children of the study population suffered from a clinically and laboratory confirmed low respiratory infection during the time of sample collection (Table 1).

Pharyngeal swabs samples were obtained from children using Sterile Catch-All™ Sample collection Swabs. A consistent methodology for processing and storage of all samples was used. Samples were immediately placed at -80°C until DNA extraction. Samples were only subjected to a single free-thaw cycle.

DNA extraction

For each subject, pharyngeal aspirates were collected and total genomic DNA was extracted from 200 µl of sample according to the manufacturer's recommended procedure using the Qiagen DNA mini kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). The DNA was eluted in 100 µl of AE elution buffer (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) and stored at -20°C until use. Total DNA concentration of each DNA extract was measured using Qubit fluorometer (Life Technologies Corporation, Carlsbad, CA, USA) with the Qubit dsDNA HS assay (Life Technologies Corporation, Carlsbad, CA, USA).

16S rRNA amplicon preparation, sequencing, and analysis

Library preparation

DNA libraries for next-generation sequencing were

constructed using two primer sets that selectively amplify the corresponding hypervariable regions of the 16s rRNA region in bacteria (V2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9). The primers used for amplification contained adaptors for Ion Torrent sequencing and Ion Xpress barcodes so that the PCR products could be pooled and sequenced directly. For the library preparation, the end repair and then purification of pooled amplicons with AMPure beads, ligation of Ion Xpress barcode adapters and nick-repair, using Ion Plus Fragment Library kit (Life Technologies Corporation, Carlsbad, CA, USA) were performed. Purification was done using AMPure beads (Agencourt), DNA was eluted in low Tris-EDTA (TE) buffer, and quantified by using a Qubit dsDNA HS (high sensitivity) kit (Life Technologies Corporation, Carlsbad, CA, USA). The library concentration was determined using Ion Universal Library Quantification kit (Life Technologies Corporation, Carlsbad, CA, USA) in an ABI7500 real time PCR system. The two resulting PCR libraries were pooled in equimolar concentrations after DNA purification.

Template preparation and sequencing

Before emulsion PCR, the library concentration was adjusted to 26 pM. Template preparation was performed in Ion 400 Template One-Touch 2 following enrichment of the amplified Ion Sphere Particles using Dynalbeads MyOne Streptavidin C1 beads (Life Technologies Corporation, Carlsbad, CA, USA) using the Ion One-Touch ES system according to the manufacturer's protocol.

The Ion Xpress barcoded library was sequenced using PGM, Ion Torrent platform (Life Technologies Corporation, Carlsbad, CA, USA). Barcoded samples were pooled and loaded into each 316 chip (Life Technologies, MA, USA) using the Ion PGM 400 Sequen-

Table 1 Demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population

ID	Status	Age	Gender	Nationality	Influenza Vaccination	Respiratory System Infection	Medical History
S02	Control	11	Female	Greek	No	No	No
S03	Control	5	Female	Greek	No	No	No
S04	Control	9	Male	Greek	No	No	No
S05	Patient	16	Male	Greek	No	Yes (Low Respiratory Tract Infection)	No
S06	Patient	6	Male	Greek	No	Yes (Low Respiratory Tract Infection)	No
S07	Control	9	Male	Greek	No	No	No
S08	Control	11	Female	Greek	No	No	No

cing Kit (Life Technologies Corporation, Carlsbad, CA, USA), according to the recommended protocol.

16s rRNA sequence data preprocessing

Base calling and run demultiplexing were performed by using Torrent Server software. The sequences were analysed using the metagenomics workflow in the Ion Reporter™ Software that enables the identification, at the genus or species level, of microbes present in complex multi-bacterial samples, and uses both the premium curated MicroSEQ™ ID 16S rRNA reference database and the curated Greengenes database.

Sequencing of the 10 human nasopharyngeal samples on the Ion Torrent PGM instrument generated 525.161 total raw reads. Raw reads were processed using the Ion Reporter software, which performs demultiplexing and denoising, quality filtering, alignment against a reference database of 16SrRNA gene sequences and clustering into operational taxonomic units (OTUs) at 97% similarity. OTUs were assigned taxonomy using the Greengenes database and analysis was performed using Quantitative Insights into Microbial Ecology (QIIME).

16S rRNA sequencing data analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted with open source programming R Language Version 3.3.1. Additionally, the following R packages were imported to further explore the microbial data: vegan Version 2.4.2, phyloseq Version 1.19.1. and ggplot2 Version 2.2.1.^{5,6,7} Bar plots and Venn diagrams were designed to explore the relative abundance of the taxa at phylum, family, genus and species level. To detect differences in abundance among subgroups of the subjects, non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was implemented

Results

In total, 459 OTUs were generated and were available for further analysis. In total, ten phyla were identified in the eight study subjects. The most abundant phyla detected, were *Firmicutes* (55.25%), *Proteobacteria* (17.03%) and *Bacteroidetes* (16.24%), followed by *Fusobacteria* (7.14%) and *Actinobacteria* (3.80%). The remaining 5 phyla *Cyanobacteria*, *Chloroflexi*, *Tenericutes*, *Spirochaetes* and *Nitrospirae* contributed less than 1.0% to the total abundance (Table 2).

At the family level, 59 families were identified, grouped together into ten phyla. The five most abundant families in healthy children were *Streptococcaceae* (41.93%), *Prevotellaceae* (14.50%), *Neisseriaceae* (8.82%), *Pasteurellaceae* (6.53%) and *Veillonellaceae* (6.23%). The five most abundant families in patients were *Pre-*

Table 2 The most abundant phyla detected in the study population

Phyla	Total Reads	Percentage
Firmicutes	139837	55.25%
Proteobacteria	43098	17.03%
Bacteroidetes	41098	16.24%
Fusobacteria	18059	7.14%
Actinobacteria	9622	3.80%
Cyanobacteria	1103	0.44%
Chloroflexi	199	0.08%
Tenericutes	47	0.02%
Spirochaetes	22	0.01%
Nitrospirae	12	0.005%

votellaceae (26.95%), *Veillonellaceae* (15.26%), *Streptococcaceae* (10.78%), *Campylobacteraceae* (8.96%) and *Nostocaceae* (8.90%) (Figure 1).

Kruskal-Wallis test that was used to compare relative abundance of families between patients and controls, did not denote statistical significant sizable differences between patients and controls (p-values > 0.05).

Moreover, out of the 59 families detected in the study population, 24 were common and present in both in patients and healthy children, while 28 families were unique and detected only in controls and seven of them only in patients (Figure 2).

At genus level, 51 genera were detected in total. The ten most abundant genera detected in healthy subjects versus patients are presented in Table 3. Further analysis revealed that 19 genera were common in both groups while 24 genera were detected only in healthy subjects and eight genera only in patients (Figure 3).

At the species level, 71 species were identified in total in the eight study subjects, while 9 of them were unique in patients (*Prevotella pleuritidis*, *Actinomyces oris*, *Prevotella nigrescens*, *Ixora taiwanensis*, *Fictibacillus rigui*, *Flavobacterium hercynium*, *Paenibacillus terrae* and *Flavobacterium succinicans*).

Regarding exploration of relative abundance within gender, no statistically significant difference was found. At the phylum level, Firmicutes were mostly detected in female, while Proteobacteria were the most abundant phylum in male, but without any statistically significant difference. Moreover, 25 families were present only in the female study group, while 11 only in male (p>0.05).

Additionally, no statistical difference was observed in the diversity of bacterial microbiota according to the age of the study group (p>0.05).

Figure 3 Venn diagram showed 8 unique genera in patients, 28 unique families in controls and 7 unique families in patients

Table 3 Ten most abundant genera detected in controls versus patients

10 Most abundant genera in controls			10 Most abundant genera in patients		
Genus	Total Reads	Percentage	Genus	Total Reads	Percentage
Streptococcus	92911	45.26%	Prevotella	3017	36.92%
Prevotella	33644	16.39%	Veillonella	1564	19.14%
Moraxella	14877	7.25%	Streptococcus	1111	13.60%
Veillonella	14038	6.84%	Campylobacter	1015	12.42%
Leptotrichia	12217	5.95%	Flavobacterium	306	3.74%
Gemella	9004	4.39%	Tepidimonas	273	3.34%
Haemophilus	6430	3.13%	Atopobium	269	3.29%
Fusobacterium	4881	2.38%	Megasphaera	106	1.30%
Granulicatella	2850	1.39%	Fusobacterium	74	0.91%
Actinomyces	2650	1.29%	Oribacterium	71	0.87%

Discussion

The upper respiratory tract (URT) is colonized by a large variety of bacteria, mostly without any pathogenic role, but there is also a number of bacteria, such

as *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Haemophilus influenzae* and *Staphylococcus aureus*, that can colonise the URT asymptotically, having the potential to cause disease.⁸ This potential role of commensal flora in the regulation of respiratory health was not evaluated until

recently, when high-throughput sequencing methods have made it possible to study the whole composition of the URT microbial ecosystem.⁹

Similar to the gut microbiome, it has been shown that colonisation of the URT begins in the first days of life, with subsequent modifications commencing for several months.¹⁰

However, initial colonisation can vary from child to child. In children whose nasopharyngeal flora remains stable, the risk of colonisation by pathogenic bacteria seems to be low, while in contrast, when profound changes occur and the initial colonisers disappear, the emergence of bacteria that cause respiratory diseases is more frequent.¹¹

In the present study, ten (10) phyla in total were identified in the study population, with the most abundant being *Firmicutes*, *Proteobacteria*, *Bacteroidetes*, *Fusobacteria* and *Actinobacteria*.

In a similar study conducted in the Centre of Public Health Genomics in USA, across all ten subjects studied, the dominant phyla were first Firmicutes, followed by Actinobacteria and Proteobacteria, while almost 20% remained unclassified.¹² The same dominant phyla were identified in a study of the upper respiratory tract of healthy children in China, in which Firmicutes were the dominant phyla, followed by Actinobacteria and Bacteroidetes.¹³ In these studies, the relative abundance of each phylum was highly variable across the subjects, which is in accordance with our results.

At the family level, both healthy subjects and controls had *Streptococcaceae*, *Prevotellaceae* and *Veillonellaceae*, while patients also had *Campylobacteraceae* and *Nostocaceae* in abundance.

At the genus level, many studies show that URT microbiota is mostly dominated by either *Streptococcus*, *Moraxella*, *Staphylococcus*, *Corynebacterium* or *Corynebacterium* and/or *Dolosigranulum*, as all of these bacteria can be easily acquired during the perinatal period from maternal skin or vaginal microbiota.^{14,15} In the present study, the five most abundant bacteria detected in healthy children were *Streptococcus*, *Prevotella*, *Moraxella*, *Veillonella* and *Leptotrichia*. The difference in our results may suggest a role of the geographic origin in the composition of the pharyngeal microbiome, among other reasons. Moreover, in young patients *Moraxella* was not detected among the most prevalent bacteria. This is a very interesting finding, since there are many studies referring to the presence of *Moraxella* in URT and its significance. Specifically, many analyses revealed that, children with initial microbial communities with high abundance

of *Staphylococcus* and *Streptococcus* tended not to have a stable microbiota, and the disappearance of these bacteria was associated with the emergence of a Haemophilus-dominated cluster. In contrast, in children whose microbiota was initially dominated by *Moraxella*, nasopharyngeal flora remained relatively stable and colonisation by bacterial respiratory pathogens, mainly *S. pneumoniae* and *H. influenzae*, was not common, suggesting that *Moraxella* might have a potential protective effect and reduce the risk of colonisation by pathogens.¹⁵ Partially overlapping findings have been reported by another study, according to which the role ascribed to *Moraxella* was significantly different, showing that colonisation by *Moraxella* was not protective because the presence of this genus was associated with an increased risk of respiratory diseases. The reasons for this discrepancy are not clear but might be explained by the poorly defined role of *Moraxella*, which is considered a potential pathogen of mucosal diseases.^{16,17} The findings of the present study are in accordance with the studies suggesting that the specific bacteria may have a protective role in human URT.

Moreover, Hasegawa et al. indicated in their paper that the risk of disease is strictly dependent on which bacteria mainly colonise the URT and especially the nasopharynx. Comparing nasal airway samples of younger infants hospitalised for bronchiolitis with controls, found four dominant profiles: *Moraxella* (37%), (27%), *Staphylococcus* (15%) and mixed bacteria (20%). When all the collected data were analysed, taking into account many parameters (age, sex, prematurity, breastfeeding and history of systemic antibiotic use prior to the enrolment), the lowest likelihood of severe bronchiolitis was evidenced in children with *Moraxella*-dominant profiles.¹⁸

In conclusion, the URT is colonized by many different potential pathogens and is constantly exposed to environmental bacteria. This microbiota is highly diverse and varies greatly between individuals. Although it has been significantly less studied, recently collected data indicate that respiratory microbiota may contribute to health regulation and disease development in the respiratory tract. Protective and pathogenic bacteria have been identified in healthy subjects and patients. Such studies can form the basis for new approaches to fight diseases responding poorly to traditional interventions.

Υπάρχει έγγραφη συγκατάθεση των συμμετεχόντων στη μελέτη, καθώς και της Επιτροπής Βιοηθικής του Αριστοτελείου Πανεπιστημίου Θεσσαλονίκης.

Περίληψη

Μελέτη του ανθρώπινου μικροβιώματος του φάρυγγα σε παιδιά με την χρήση της τεχνικής αλληλούχισης νέας γενεάς

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Το ανώτερο αναπνευστικό σύστημα αποικίζεται από ένα μεγάλο αριθμό βακτηρίων, τα οποία διαθέτουν προστατευτικό ρόλο και χαρακτηρίζονται ως αναπνευστικό μικροβίωμα. Ο ρόλος της παρούσας μελέτης είναι η ανάλυση του μικροβιώματος και των σχετικών αναλογιών των μικροβιακών κοινοτήτων της ανατομικής περιοχής του φάρυγγα μέσω της αλληλούχισης του γονιδίου 16S rRNA με τεχνική αλληλούχισης νέας γενεάς, τόσο σε υγιή παιδιά, όσο και σε παιδιά με λοίμωξη του αναπνευστικού συστήματος. Συνολικά, δέκα φύλα βακτηρίων ταυτοποιήθηκαν σε σύνολο 8 παιδιών, με κυρίαρχα φύλα τα εξής: Firmicutes, Proteobacteria και Bacteroidetes. Σε επίπεδο οικογένειας, γένους και είδους, 24 οικογένειες, 19 γένη και 71 είδη βακτηρίων ανιχνεύθηκαν τόσο σε υγιή όσο και σε παιδιά με λοίμωξη. Είκοσι οκτώ (28) οικογένειες και 24 γένη ανιχνεύθηκαν μόνο σε υγιή άτομα, ενώ 7 οικογένειες, 8 γένη και 9 είδη μόνο ασθενείς. Δεν παρατηρήθηκε καμία στατιστικά σημαντική διαφορά ανάμεσα στο μικροβίωμα και την ηλικία ή το φύλο των ατόμων της μελέτης. Παράλληλα, τα κυρίαρχα βακτήρια που ανιχνεύθηκαν σε υγιή παιδιά ήταν ο *Streptococcus*, *Prevotella*, *Moraxella*, *Veillonella* και *Leptotrichia*, επιβεβαιώνοντας τον προστατευτικό ρόλο, κυρίως της *Moraxella* σύμφωνα και με την διεθνή βιβλιογραφία. Συμπερασματικά, παρόμοιες μελέτες θα αποτελέσουν την βάση για τον καθορισμό ενός πυρήνα μικροβιώματος ανά ανατομική αλλά και ανά γεωγραφική περιοχή, προκειμένου να οδηγηθούμε σε νέες προσεγγίσεις στην αντιμετώπιση των λοιμώξεων που δεν ανταποκρίνονται στις κλασσικές θεραπευτικές μεθόδους.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

Μικροβίωμα, 16SrRNA, αναπνευστικό σύστημα, παιδιά, αλληλούχιση

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